

Searching for Snapshots of Giant Exoplanet Migration

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NEID, an extreme precision Doppler spectrograph on the WIYN 3.5-meter Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory (a partnership between Indiana University, University of Wisconsin-Madison, Pennsylvania State University, Princeton University, Purdue University, NSF's NOIRLab, and NASA), is helping unravel the origin of hot Jupiters. These giant exoplanets, orbiting their host stars with periods of less than 10 days, have challenged our understanding of planet formation for decades. Our own gas giant neighbors, Jupiter and Saturn, could only have grown to their current size by accumulating a high mass of volatile materials that were only present in the more distant reaches of the early Solar System. Numerous theories for the formation of hot Jupiters have been proposed, many of which predict that these exoplanets formed several AU from their host stars, at similar orbital separations to Jupiter, before migrating inwards to their present locations. If so, we should expect to see not only hot Jupiters but also an intermediate population of migrating "warm" Jupiters on longer-period orbits if we surveyed enough stellar systems. The demographics of this population may hold the key to understanding which formation channels dominate. However, the population of warm Jupiters amenable to detailed study is relatively sparse, in part due to the

intrinsic rarity of planets in this class and in part because of observational biases that disfavor the detection of long-period signals.

NASA's *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite* (*TESS*) is helping to unearth a new sample of warm Jupiter candidates. I have been leading an initiative to use NEID to confirm and characterize many of these exoplanets. By first observing candidates with the NN-EXPLORE Exoplanet Stellar Speckle Imager (NESSI), also on the

WIYN 3.5-meter Telescope, we efficiently determine whether each signal detected by *TESS* is indeed an orbiting exoplanet, rather than a background source, and is thus worthy of follow-up observations. With NEID, we then monitor the stellar radial velocity (RV) signal and check for the periodic variations characteristic of an orbiting exoplanet.

In addition to the advantages conferred by NEID's exquisite Doppler precision, the logistical framework of

Figure 1: (Upper) *TESS* photometry for a warm Jupiter candidate; (Lower) Possible orbital periods and corresponding probabilities based on orbital geometry. Two transits were detected, but they are separated by 716 days. The available data allow for 35 possible period aliases, ranging from just 20 days up to the observed 716-day separation.

Figure 2: Radial velocity curve for TOI-4127 b. The final NEID measurements were strategically scheduled to capture the large velocity excursion near periastron.

NEID observations has played an important role in aiding this effort. Unlike a classically scheduled instrument, the NEID queue provides the flexibility for adjustments to be made as new data are collected and analyzed, on timescales of weeks rather than semesters. This flexibility is essential for studies of exoplanets with longer orbital periods. Because *TESS* sacrifices temporal baselines in favor of all-sky coverage, the sample we are selecting from is composed primarily of candidates for which *TESS* detected either a single transit or just a few transits separated by months to years (Figure 1). As a result, the orbital periods are initially unknown. However, as the corresponding RV signals begin to take shape, we are able to adaptively update our observing schedule and capture the exoplanets at key orbital phases to more efficiently measure their orbital parameters.

Earlier this year, we published the discovery of TOI-4127 b, the first

warm Jupiter to be confirmed through our observing program (Gupta et al. 2023). With an orbital eccentricity of $e \sim 0.75$, this planet perfectly illustrates the utility of the NEID queue, which allowed us to sample the narrow periastron passage window on very short notice (Figure 2). TOI-4127 b is of scientific interest when placed in the context of one of the most intriguing — and plausible — hot Jupiter formation channels. This channel requires that the progenitor exoplanet is first excited onto an extremely eccentric orbit such that it passes very close to the host star during periastron. During these close encounters, tidal interactions with the host star will sap energy from the orbit, causing it to shrink and circularize, ultimately producing the hot Jupiters that we see today. The discovery of HD 80606 b (Naef et al. 2001), a giant exoplanet with a highly eccentric orbit in the midst of tidally circularizing, helped create a cohesive narrative linking the observed hot Jupiter population to a

well-understood formation pathway. However, few similar systems have been identified in the intervening decades, and none as clear-cut as HD 80606 b. And despite its high orbital eccentricity, TOI-4127 b falls short as well. The orbit is still not eccentric enough for tidal migration to take hold, and the initial excitation mechanism for this system is unclear. Still, this adds a valuable point to the warm Jupiter sample, and further observations will provide more clues to its origin and trajectory.

In the coming months, we expect to share additional results from our program, including more exciting exoplanet discoveries and insights about the warm Jupiter population.

References

- Gupta, A. F., et al. 2023, *AJ*, 165, 234
- Naef, D., et al. 2001, *A&A*, 375, 27